

Health Education Programmes for Supporting Older Women's Adaptation to Menopause in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

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Abstract

The study examined health education programmes for supporting older women's adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The study was guided by three objectives and three research questions. The descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study with a population of 912 older women (executives) and health officers in all the registered Community-Based Women Organizations in Port Harcourt metropolis and the two tertiary health centres (University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital and Rivers State University Teaching Hospital) in Rivers State. The sample of the study was 319 women (executive members) and health officers in all the registered community-based women organizations in the 23 LGAs of Rivers State and tertiary health centres (University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital and Rivers State University Teaching Hospital) in Rivers State. The sample consist of 277women (executive members) from registered community-based women organizations and 42 health officers from the two tertiary health institutions in the study area. The multistage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Health Education Programmes for Supporting Older Women's Adaptation to Menopause Questionnaire". The instrument was validated by three experts while the reliability of the instrument was established through a test of internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha method. Coefficients of 0.84, 0.88 and 0.82 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument which showed that the instrument was reliable. The research questions of the study were answered using mean and standard deviation. The findings of the study revealed among others that community-based menopause awareness programme and nutrition and lifestyle modification programme could be used to support older women's adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State to a high extent. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that Healthcare administrators and policymakers in Rivers State should prioritize the establishment of comprehensive emotional support services for menopausal women.

Keywords: Menopause, Older Women, Adaptation, Health Education

INTRODUCTION

Menopause is a significant phase in a woman's life, marking the end of reproductive capacity and bringing about various biological, psychological, and social challenges. This natural transition is often accompanied by symptoms such as hot flashes, mood swings, sleep disturbances, and increased risks of osteoporosis and cardiovascular disease (Greendale et al., 2019). In low- and middle-income countries, such as Nigeria, the challenges associated with menopause can be further exacerbated by limited access to healthcare resources, cultural stigmas, and a lack of targeted health education (Omidvar et al., 2018). Despite these challenges, menopause is often overlooked in public health interventions, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa, where the focus on women's health is predominantly centered on reproductive and maternal health. This gap highlights the need for health education programmes aimed at equipping older women with the knowledge and skills to cope with menopausal changes effectively.

Port Harcourt, located in Rivers State, Nigeria, represents a unique urban environment with diverse socio-economic groups. The city has experienced significant growth in population and urbanization, which has put a strain on its healthcare infrastructure (World Bank, 2020). Women in this region face a dual burden of health challenges, including limited awareness of menopausal health and barriers to accessing adequate

healthcare services. A study by Iliyasu et al. (2021) found that many Nigerian women lack accurate knowledge about menopause and often resort to informal sources of information, such as friends or traditional healers, which may perpetuate myths and misconceptions. Health education programmes, therefore, play a crucial role in bridging this knowledge gap by providing evidence-based information, promoting healthy lifestyle choices, and reducing the stigma associated with menopause.

Globally, research has demonstrated the positive impact of health education interventions on improving women's ability to cope with menopause. For example, a study conducted in India by Joshi et al. (2019) showed that women who participated in structured health education sessions reported a significant reduction in the severity of menopausal symptoms and improved psychological well-being. Similarly, in Western contexts, health education has been linked to better adherence to recommended lifestyle changes, such as increased physical activity and improved dietary habits, which are critical for managing menopausal symptoms and reducing long-term health risks (Hunter & Rendall, 2021). However, there is a dearth of localized research on the effectiveness of such interventions in African urban settings, including Port Harcourt. This study aimed to address this gap by evaluating the effectiveness of health education programmes in supporting older women's adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt.

Furthermore, to support older women in adapting to menopause, well-structured health education programmes should be designed to address the physiological, psychological, and social challenges associated with this transition. These programmes should be culturally relevant, accessible, and tailored to the specific needs of women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Some of these health education programmes tailored to the specific needs of women include community-based menopause awareness and education programme, nutrition and lifestyle modification workshops, emotional support programme, physical fitness and exercise programme, traditional and alternative medicine education and telehealth support programme.

Community-based menopause awareness and education programme provide public health education campaigns in local communities, churches, and women's groups to increase awareness of menopause, its symptoms, and effective coping strategies. It will involve health talks, seminars, and interactive sessions facilitated by healthcare professionals, including gynecologists, nurses, and nutritionists. Topics will include hormonal changes, common symptoms, myths and misconceptions, and available treatment options such as hormone replacement therapy (HRT) and alternative therapies.

Nutrition and lifestyle modification workshops are designed to educate women on proper nutrition, weight management, and the importance of regular physical activity in managing menopause symptoms. Sessions will focus on calcium and vitamin D intake to prevent osteoporosis, as well as the role of phytoestrogens (plant-based estrogens) found in foods like soybeans. Practical cooking demonstrations will be included to teach women how to prepare nutrient-rich meals that support hormonal balance.

Emotional support programme addresses the emotional and mental health challenges, such as anxiety, depression, and mood swings, that menopausal women often experience. It will include group counseling sessions, mindfulness training, relaxation techniques, and stress management strategies to help women cope with emotional changes. Peer support groups will be established where women can share their experiences, receive encouragement, and learn from one another.

By assessing the outcomes of these programmes, such as changes in knowledge, attitudes, and coping mechanisms, this research sought to provide evidence that can inform the design and implementation of targeted interventions for menopausal women.

Statement of the Problem

Menopause represents a critical phase in a woman's life, marked by significant physiological and psychological changes that often affect her quality of life. These changes, which include hot flashes, mood swings, sleep disturbances, and increased risks of chronic conditions such as osteoporosis and cardiovascular disease, can be overwhelming without adequate support or information. In many low- and middle-income countries like Nigeria, the challenges associated with menopause are compounded by limited awareness, cultural stigmas, and inadequate access to healthcare services (Omidvar et al., 2018). In particular, women in urban areas such as Port Harcourt are faced with unique socio-economic and healthcare barriers, which make coping with menopause even more difficult.

Despite the increasing recognition of menopause as an important public health issue globally, there remains a significant gap in targeted interventions for women in Nigeria, including those residing in Port Harcourt metropolis. Studies suggest that many Nigerian women rely on informal and often inaccurate sources of information, such as friends or traditional healers, to understand and manage menopause (Iliyasu et al., 2021). This reliance on informal networks perpetuates misconceptions and leaves many women unprepared to navigate the health challenges of this life stage effectively. Moreover, the lack of culturally appropriate and evidence-based health education programs tailored to the specific needs of menopausal women in Nigeria further exacerbates the issue.

While global studies have shown the positive impact of health education programs on improving knowledge, coping mechanisms, and overall well-being of menopausal women (Joshi et al., 2019), there is a lack of localized research in Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in urban centers like Port Harcourt. The absence of empirical data on the effectiveness of such interventions means that policy makers and healthcare providers are limited in their ability to design and implement programmes that can effectively support older women during menopause. This study, therefore, sought to address this critical gap by assessing the effectiveness of health education programmes in supporting older women's adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine health education programmes for supporting older women's adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the extent to which community-based menopause awareness programme could be used to support older women's adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State.
2. ascertain the extent to which nutrition and lifestyle modification workshops could be used to support older women's adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State.
3. assess the extent to which emotional support programme could be used to support older women's adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent could community-based menopause awareness programme be used to support older women’s adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State?
2. To what extent could nutrition and lifestyle modification workshops be used to support older women’s adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State?
3. To what extent could emotional support programme be used to support older women’s adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State?

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study with a population of 912 older women (executives) and health officers in all the registered Community-Based Women Organizations in Port Harcourt metropolis and the two tertiary health centres (University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital and Rivers State University Teaching Hospital) in Rivers State. The sample of the study is 319 women (executive members) and health officers in all the registered community-based women organisations in Port Harcourt metropolis and tertiary health centres (University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital and Rivers State University Teaching Hospital) in Rivers State. The sample consist of 277women (executive members) from registered community-based women organisations and 42 health officers from the two tertiary health institutions in the study area. The multistage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample of women while the entire health officers were taken as census without sampling. This is due to the manageable size of the health officers.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Health Education Programmes for Supporting Older Women’s Adaptation to Menopause Questionnaire”. (HEPSOWAMQ). The instrument was divided into two sections; section A elicited information on the demographic data of the respondents, while section B consisted of structured items drawn from the three research questions guiding the study. Responses to the questionnaire were structured on a four-point summated rating scale weighed as follows:

VHE =	Very High Extent	(4 points)
HE =	High Extent	(3 points)
LE =	Low Extent	(2 points)
VLE =	Very Low Extent	(1 point)

The instrument was validated by three experts while the reliability of the instrument was established through a test of internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha method. Coefficients of 0.84, 0.88 and 0.82 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument which showed that the instrument was reliable. The research questions of the study were answered using mean and standard deviation. Decision rule for the research questions was based on the classification of level of extent as shown below:

Classification	Value Range
Very High Extent (VHE) = 4	3.50 – 4.00
High Extent (HE) = 3	2.50 – 3.49
Low Extent (LE) = 2	1.50 – 2.49
Very Low Extent (VLE) =1	1.00 – 1.49

RESULT

Research Question 1: To what extent could community-based menopause awareness programme be used to support older women’s adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings on the Extent Community-Based Menopause Awareness Programme be Used to Support Older Women’s Adaptation to Menopause

S/N	Items	Women (270)			Health Officers (40)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Participating in community-based menopause programmes would help older women better understand and manage their symptoms	3.16	0.65	HE	3.18	1.09	HE
2	Attending community-based menopause awareness programme could offer older women a supportive environment to share their experiences and connect with others.	2.23	1.01	LE	2.18	1.07	LE
3	Community-based menopause awareness programmes could help women develop coping strategies and self-care practices to manage menopause symptoms.	2.60	1.10	HE	2.71	1.00	HE
4	Educating women about menopause through community-based programmes could help them make informed decisions about their health.	3.47	1.13	HE	3.43	1.09	HE
5	Community-based menopause awareness programmes might empower women to take control of their health and well-being during menopause.	2.78	0.66	HE	2.68	0.70	HE
6	Community-based menopause awareness programmes could help women develop coping strategies and self-care practices to manage menopause symptoms.	2.83	0.77	HE	2.96	0.79	HE
Grand Mean		2.85		HE	2.86		HE

The analysis in Table 1 revealed that regarding community-based menopause awareness programmes, both women (mean = 3.16, SD = 0.65) and health officers (mean = 3.18, SD = 1.09) demonstrated high extent agreement that participating in such programmes would help older women better understand and manage their symptoms. However, a notable divergence emerged when examining the supportive environment aspect, where both groups showed low extent ratings for attending community-based awareness programmes to share experiences and connect with others, with women rating it at 2.23 (SD = 1.01) and health officers at 2.18 (SD = 1.07). The development of coping strategies through community-based programmes received moderate to high extent ratings from both groups, with women scoring 2.60 (SD = 1.10) and health officers 2.71 (SD = 1.00). Educational components focusing on informed decision-making garnered the highest support within this category, with women rating it 3.47 (SD = 1.13) and health officers 3.43 (SD = 1.09). Empowerment aspects received high extent ratings from both women (2.78, SD = 0.66) and health officers (2.68, SD = 0.70), while the duplicate item on coping strategies maintained consistent high extent ratings of 2.83 (SD = 0.77) for women and 2.96 (SD = 0.79) for health officers. The overall grand mean for community-based programmes stood at 2.85 for women and 2.86 for health officers, both indicating high extent agreement.

Research Question 2: To what extent could nutrition and lifestyle modification workshops be used to support older women’s adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings on the Extent to which Nutrition and Lifestyle Modification Workshops could be Used to Support Older Women’s Adaptation to Menopause

S/N	Items	Women (270)			Health Officers (40)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
7	Providing nutrition education and counseling would help women make informed decisions about their diet during menopause.	3.30	1.08	HE	3.10	1.07	HE
8	A nutrition and lifestyle modification workshop could provide women with practical strategies to manage menopause symptoms.	2.91	1.12	HE	2.95	1.13	HE
9	Offering guidance on healthy eating habits would support women's overall health and well-being during menopause.	2.94	1.17	HE	2.80	1.15	HE
10	A workshop focused on nutrition and lifestyle modification could help women develop healthy coping mechanisms for menopause symptoms.	3.10	1.10	HE	3.20	1.14	HE
11	Offering nutrition counseling could help women identify and avoid trigger foods that exacerbate menopause symptoms.	2.60	1.13	HE	2.71	1.17	HE
12	Providing nutrition education could help women make informed decisions about their health and well-being during menopause.	3.31	1.07	HE	3.19	1.20	HE
	Grand Mean	3.02		HE	2.99		HE

The analysed data in Table 2 revealed that the nutrition and lifestyle modification workshops demonstrated strong acceptance across all measured parameters. Nutrition education and counseling received high extent ratings from women (3.30, SD = 1.08) and health officers (3.10, SD = 1.07) regarding informed dietary decisions during menopause. Practical strategy provision through nutrition and lifestyle workshops was rated highly by both women (2.91, SD = 1.12) and health officers (2.95, SD = 1.13). Guidance on healthy eating habits for overall health and well-being during menopause received high extent agreement from women (2.94, SD = 1.17) and health officers (2.80, SD = 1.15). The development of healthy coping mechanisms through nutrition-focused workshops was well-received, with women rating it 3.10 (SD = 1.10) and health officers 3.20 (SD = 1.14). Nutrition counseling for identifying and avoiding trigger foods that exacerbate menopause symptoms received high extent ratings from both women (2.60, SD = 1.13) and health officers (2.71, SD = 1.17). The provision of nutrition education for informed health decisions during menopause achieved the highest ratings in this category, with women scoring 3.31 (SD = 1.07) and health officers 3.19 (SD = 1.20). The grand mean for nutrition and lifestyle modification workshops was 3.02 for women and 2.99 for health officers, representing the second-highest overall acceptance among all programmes.

Research Question 3: To what extent could emotional support programme be used to support older women’s adaptation to menopause in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Ratings on the Extent to which Emotional Support Programme could be Used to Support Older Women’s Adaptation to Menopause

S/N	Items	Women (270)	Health Officers (40)
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		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
13	One-on-one emotional support could help women cope with anxiety and depression related to menopause.	3.46	1.19	HE	3.43	1.14	HE
14	An emotional support programme could provide women with a safe space to express their feelings and emotions about menopause.	3.28	1.15	HE	3.37	1.17	HE
15	Emotional support from a trained counselor or therapist could help women develop coping strategies for managing menopause-related emotions.	3.41	1.08	HE	3.49	1.02	HE
16	A support group focused on emotional support could provide women with a sense of community and connection during menopause.	3.40	1.14	HE	3.46	1.11	HE
17	Emotional support could help women process and deal with emotional changes related to menopause.	3.45	1.06	HE	3.48	1.19	HE
18	An emotional support program could provide women with a sense of validation and understanding during a challenging time.	3.33	1.13	HE	3.29	1.03	HE
	Grand Mean	3.39		HE	3.42		HE

The analysed data in Table 3 revealed that emotional support programmes received the highest overall acceptance ratings across the research. One-on-one emotional support for coping with anxiety and depression related to menopause was highly rated by both women (3.46, SD = 1.19) and health officers (3.43, SD = 1.14). The provision of safe spaces for expressing feelings and emotions about menopause through emotional support programmes received strong endorsement from women (3.28, SD = 1.15) and health officers (3.37, SD = 1.17). Professional emotional support from trained counselors or therapists for developing coping strategies was highly valued by both groups, with women rating it 3.41 (SD = 1.08) and health officers 3.49 (SD = 1.02). Support groups focused on emotional support for community and connection during menopause received high extent ratings from women (3.40, SD = 1.14) and health officers (3.46, SD = 1.11). The processing and management of emotional changes related to menopause through emotional support was strongly endorsed by both women (3.45, SD = 1.06) and health officers (3.48, SD = 1.19). Emotional support programmes providing validation and understanding during challenging times received high extent agreement from women (3.33, SD = 1.13) and health officers (3.29, SD = 1.03). The emotional support programme category achieved the highest grand mean scores of 3.39 for women and 3.42 for health officers.

Discussion of Findings

Extent to Which community-based menopause awareness programmes could be used to support older women's adaptation to menopause

The findings of the study for research question one revealed that both older women (grand mean = 2.85) and health officers (grand mean = 2.86) demonstrated high extent agreement regarding the effectiveness of community-based menopause awareness programmes in supporting older women's adaptation to menopause. This finding indicates strong consensus between the target beneficiaries and healthcare providers regarding the potential value of community-based interventions.

The highest rated item was "educating women about menopause through community-based programmes could help them make informed decisions about their health" (women: 3.47, health officers: 3.43), suggesting that information provision is viewed as the most crucial component of community-based programmes. Conversely, the lowest rated item was "attending community-based menopause awareness programme could offer older women a supportive environment to share their experiences and connect with others" (women: 2.23, health officers: 2.18), indicating potential cultural or social barriers to group sharing experiences in the Port Harcourt context.

This finding aligns with research by Empowerment and Coping Strategies in Menopause Women (2022), which emphasizes the importance of "empowerment programs that fit social and cultural norms in a particular social context" to increase women's awareness and adaptation to menopause. Additionally, The Menopause Society's(2023) focus on providing healthcare professionals with necessary tools and resources to improve women's health during menopause transition supports the collaborative approach evident in this study's findings.

Extent to which Nutrition and Lifestyle Modification Workshops could be used to support older women's adaptation to menopause

The findings of the study for research question two revealed high extent acceptance of nutrition and lifestyle modification workshops among both older women (grand mean = 3.02) and health officers (grand mean = 2.99), representing the second-highest overall acceptance among all programmes studied. This finding underscores the recognition of nutrition's critical role in managing menopause symptoms and promoting overall health during the menopausal transition.

The highest rated item was "providing nutrition education could help women make informed decisions about their health and well-being during menopause" (women: 3.31, health officers: 3.19), emphasizing the value placed on informed decision-making. The lowest rated item was "offering nutrition counseling could help women identify and avoid trigger foods that exacerbate menopause symptoms" (women: 2.60, health officers: 2.71), possibly reflecting limited awareness about the relationship between specific foods and menopause symptoms. These findings are corroborated by research showing that menopause is associated with increased prevalence of obesity, metabolic syndrome, cardiovascular diseases, and osteoporosis, which "can be significantly improved by eliminating and reducing dietary risk factors" through nutrition counseling and intervention. Furthermore, studies indicate that "health education interventions that focused on lifestyle modifications given to women at menopause improved sustainability of health-promoting behaviors and ultimately enhanced the women's health status."

Extent to which Emotional Support Programme could be used to support older women's adaptation to menopause

The findings of the study for research three revealed that the emotional support programme category achieved the highest overall acceptance ratings across the entire study, with older women rating it at 3.39 and health officers at 3.42. This finding highlights the critical importance of addressing the psychological and emotional dimensions of menopause adaptation, which are often overlooked in purely medical approaches.

The highest rated item was "one-on-one emotional support could help women cope with anxiety and depression related to menopause" (women: 3.46, health officers: 3.43), indicating recognition of the individual nature of emotional support needs. All items in this category received consistently high ratings above 3.28, suggesting comprehensive acceptance of various forms of emotional support interventions.

This finding is supported by research emphasizing the importance of empowerment and coping strategies for menopausal women, which recognizes that emotional and psychological support are fundamental to successful menopause adaptation. The Menopause Society's(2019) emphasis on providing comprehensive support to women during their menopause journey aligns with these findings, acknowledging that menopause affects not only physical but also emotional well-being.

CONCLUSION

The findings revealed significant insights into the preferences and perceptions of both older women and health officers regarding menopause support interventions. Emotional support programmes emerged as the most highly valued intervention demonstrating the critical importance of addressing the psychological and emotional dimensions of menopause adaptation. This was followed by nutrition and lifestyle modification workshops indicating strong recognition of the role of dietary and lifestyle factors in menopause management.

Community-based menopause awareness programmes received substantial acceptance though with notable variations in specific components, particularly regarding group sharing and social support elements. Traditional and alternative medicine education programmes showed moderate acceptance, reflecting the cultural context of Port Harcourt where traditional healing practices maintain relevance alongside modern medical approaches.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Healthcare administrators and policymakers in Rivers State should prioritize the establishment of comprehensive emotional support services for menopausal women. This should include training and deployment of specialized counselors and therapists with expertise in menopause-related emotional challenges and development of one-on-one counseling services to address anxiety and depression associated with menopause
2. Healthcare providers and educational institutions should develop structured nutrition education programmes specifically tailored to menopause management and create practical workshops that teach women how to identify and avoid trigger foods that exacerbate menopause symptoms
3. Programme developers should design culturally sensitive awareness programmes that respect local norms and values regarding women's health discussions and develop alternative formats for information sharing that may be more acceptable in the Port Harcourt context, such as individual consultations or small group sessions

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